

Study of sleep pattern and suicidal ideation among opioid dependents

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Abstract

Suicide and sleep issues have been linked in a number of earlier research. This correlation has not, however, been particularly studied in opioid users. It has been revealed in the studies of many authors that the opioid dependent people have sleep disturbances and are thus more prone to suicidal attempts as compared to non dependents, thus it becomes vital to study the effect of sleep disturbances, suicidal ideation among the opioid dependents. Sleep is a mechanism that has been preserved throughout evolution and is crucial for numerous biological processes to relax and recover. Alterations in sleep and alertness have a role in starting and sustaining drug and alcohol usage as well as in raising the likelihood of relapse. During withdrawal and cessation, opioid-dependent people typically lament having trouble falling or staying asleep. Even people on opioid substitution therapy (OST) report having sleep problems. The purpose of this study is to outline variables related to sleep disruption and to provide an overview of sleep issues experienced by patients who are opioid dependent. This study offered some evidence for a link between sleep problems and suicidal thoughts. To better comprehend how opioid users' sleep disturbance, suicidal ideas, preparations, and attempts work, the study's findings may be useful for educational and public health preventative programmes. Finding risk factors and achieving the overarching goal of harm reduction among opioid abusers can both be aided by further study.

Keywords: Sleep patterns; Opioid dependents, Suicidal Ideation; Sleep disturbance, Opioid

Introduction:

In all states, the opioid crisis is becoming worse and is increasingly posing a threat to public health (Rudd, Seth, David, & Scholl 2015). Between 1999 and 2014, the number of drug overdose deaths tripled. The Bohnert et al. (2013) study on opioid intake for reasons related to pain vs. for reasons unrelated to pain relief among addiction therapy patients may offer insights on the informal consumption of opioids among abusers. there are several reasons why people take opioids, such as for social enhancement or enjoyment, to minimise the emotional pain brought on by depressed symptoms, and to cope with upsetting situations and feelings. In addition, people with a history of drug misuse or mental illness were more likely to take opioids non-medically for diseases other than pain.

Patients in rehab for addiction who abuse opioids for purposes other than treating pain reported taking higher dosages of the medicines compared to individuals who solely utilise them to relieve pain. The prevalence of mental health issues is also greater among opioid addicts who take the medications for purposes other than treating pain (Bohnert et al., 2013). The usage of opioids is causing serious worries about drug overdose mortality (Cheatle, 2011). For instance, prior research involving opioid users raises the possibility that using opioids and having sleep issues are related (Bernert, 2008). This finding is especially troubling in light of the mounting evidence that suicide and sleep disturbances are strongly related. It's possible that using opioids, having trouble sleeping, and having suicide thoughts, plans, or attempts are related. This connection hasn't, however, been particularly studied in opioid users. It has been revealed in the studies of many authors that the opioid dependent people have sleep disturbances and are thus more prone to suicidal attempts as compared to non dependents, thus it becomes vital to study the effect of sleep disturbances, suicidal ideation among the opioid dependents.. The purpose of this study is to look at the relationship between disturbed sleep and opioid users' suicide ideas, plans, and attempts.

Literature Review:

Given its usefulness in treating a range of pain problems, opioids are widely administered. A severe headache or migraine was the most frequent type of pain, followed by neck pain (19%), facial discomfort or pain (6%), and low back pain (32%), (National Institute of Health Statistics).

Kosten, T., & George, T. (2002) Adults who suffer from low back pain frequently have lower mental and physical wellness than those who do not. The same study that determined low back pain to be the main source of pain found that one hundred million individuals have chronic pain. Franklin, G. M. (2014), the prevalence of lower back pain rose over the course of the 14-year period, rising from 3.9% in 1992 to 10.2% in 2014. Men and women of all adult ages, in addition to black and white racial groups, all shown increases. Despite the fact that more people are using opioids on prescription since 1999, they continue to report experiencing the same amount of pain. Barbour et al. (2016) state that 10.5 million people reported having severe joint pain in the CDC health survey conducted in 2002, and that figure rose to 14.5 million in 2014. Robinson et al. (2017), Middle-aged and older persons account for 75% of the population with chronic pain, and they are the most vulnerable. As previously mentioned, variables including socio demographics, The same factors that are more likely to affect women and people of color compared to how likely they are to affect men and also have a bearing on the effects of chronic pain are medical history, healthcare use and access, self-management challenges, and social support. Women were twice as likely as men to experience migraines (severe headaches), facial or jaw pain (National Health Interview Survey, 2009). Johannes et al. (2010), in their internet-based survey, stated that some of the groups expressed discomfort more frequently than others. Women, persons with impairments, those with low incomes, and those without jobs have a 20% higher likelihood of having chronic pain than any other category. Johannes, Le, Zhou, a Johnston, and Dworkin (2010) People between the ages of 55 to 65 are threefold more likely to experience discomfort than people between the ages of 18 to 24. Nearly 100 million people suffer from persistent discomfort, and even a small number of individuals who get addicted to opioids have a detrimental effect on public health. Volkow, (2014) Opioids also provide users a sense of happiness and pleasure because they directly stimulate the rewards centre of the brain. These results are comparable to those of some illicit substances, such heroin. Studies on the usage of opioids support scientifically supported conclusions that opioid misuse has contributed to a heroin pandemic in several regions.

Definition of opioid

Opioids constitute a class of medications with a strong emphasis on managing pain, and they carry a high risk of addiction. 2017 opioids are created naturally from the plant that produces

opium poppy seeds, semi-synthetically from 11 plants that serve as starting points, and synthetically from full synthetic and chemical building blocks. According to the NIDA, using opioids for purposes other than those for which they were prescribed, taking them with a different authorization, or taking them for the purpose of getting high are all examples of opioid abuse. When used as directed by a doctor, opioids are quite effective in treating pain for a brief period of time.

Opioids taken improperly can increase reliance and addiction (NIDA, 2017). Opioids are more hazardous and opioid abusers are more susceptible to issues including overdose fatalities and injuries due to the impacts of addiction, such as a lack of willpower, mental incapacity, or increased hunger, reduced reasoning, and abnormal emotional reaction.

Opioid usage epidemiology

More than 30% of population, experience chronic pain at some point in their lives, according to Volkow and McLellan (2014). In addition, they discovered that retail pharmacies filled 74 million opioid prescriptions in 1994 as opposed to the most current estimates of 234 million opioid prescriptions in 2014. 62% of those prescriptions were for short-term opioid therapy, while 8.7 million to 13.4 million adults were found to be receiving longer-term opioid medication, according to the research.

As a result of the rise in opioid use, there are now more fatalities related to opioid addiction and misuse. Nearly half of the fifty-five thousand drug overdose fatalities in 2013 were caused by opioid use, while heroin use contributed to 24% of fatalities. The present opioid addiction crisis is to blame for the opioid overdose deaths. According to Volkow and McLellan, an opioid overdose harmed 1.9 million persons in 2014.

Volkow and McLellan (2016), heroin is sometimes simpler to get and is often less expensive than opioids. Heroin usage commonly follows opioid misuse which results, a very small percentage (6%) of addicts switch to heroin, although that number is increasing. Doctors' prescriptions are the primary supply of opioids, and several doctors and medical organisations have also published detailed recommendations for prescribing opioids and treating chronic pain. Opioid usage frequently stems from consumers "doctor shopping" or visiting various pharmacies in order to obtain prescriptions.

Many doctors also acknowledged that they lack the knowledge necessary to safely prescribe opioids, identify misuse or addiction, or even properly inform patients about the risks associated with opioid use. People with opioid addiction who temporarily refrain from using them are nonetheless at danger of overdosing on opioids. Opioid withdrawal reverses Within days or weeks, tolerance and physical dependency set in, but for opioid clients, the fundamental effects of addiction continue for years. Early interventions among opioid users are required to address issues connected to opioid usage since the risk of overdose is higher in inmates after being released from prison and in those who complete detoxification programmes.

Research Methodology

The goal of this paper is to study the sleep patterns and suicidal ideation among opuoid dependents. Data for same was collected from the 200 respondents from Delhi. Each volunteer received an assurance that their answers would be kept private and never used over any other reason. In this research study, a descriptive survey method was employed to find the sleep patterns and suicidal ideation among opioid dependents. To find out research objective data was analyzed by Pearson correlation and chi sq test.

Objectives:

1. To identify the levels of sleep patterns and suicidal ideation among opioid dependents
2. To measure the effects of opioid drug dependence on sleep patterns and suicidal ideation.
3. To examine the relationship between sleep patterns and suicidal ideation among opioid dependence

Hypothesis Testing

H1- The levels of sleep patterns and suicidal ideation will be high among opioid dependents

			Frequency	Percent	Valid	Cumulative
Sleep Patterns	Valid	Low	77	38.5	38.5	38.5
		High	123	61.5	61.5	100
		Total	200	100	100	
Suicidal Ideation	Valid	Low	79	39.5	39.5	39.5
		High	121	60.5	60.5	100
		Total	200	100	100	

Table no 1 depicts that the level of sleep patterns in 38.5 % of respondents is low and 61.5 % of respondents is high and the level of suicidal ideation in 39.5 % of respondents is low and 60.5 % of respondents is high

H2- There is significant correlation between sleep patterns and suicidal ideation among opioid dependence

		Suicidal Ideation
Sleep patterns	Pearson Correlation	0.359**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00
	N	200
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)		

Table no 2 depicts that there is positive relation between Sleep patterns and Suicidal Ideation among opioid dependents and the sig value is 0.00.

H3- There is a significant effect of opioid drug on sleep patterns among opioid dependents.

		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Opioid drug * sleep patterns	Pearson Chi-Square	1425.362	795	.000
	Likelihood Ratio	265.179	795	0.989
	Linear-by-Linear Association	18.365	1	.000
	N of Valid Cases	200		

As shown in table 3 above the p value for effect of opioid drug on sleep patterns among opioid dependents is 0.00.

H4- There is a significant effect of opioid drug on suicidal ideation among opioid dependents.

		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Opioid drug * suicidal ideation	Pearson Chi-Square	1935.324	795	.000
	Likelihood Ratio	325.126	795	1.000
	Linear-by-Linear Association	16.253	1	.000
	N of Valid Cases	200		

As shown in table 4 above the p value for effect of opioid drug on suicidal ideation among opioid dependents is 0.00.

Findings

Table no 1 depicts that the level of sleep patterns in 38.5 % of respondents is low and 61.5 % of respondents is high and the level of suicidal ideation in 39.5 % of respondents is low and 60.5 % of respondents is high, thus here accepting the alternate hypothesis H1 is accepted which claims

that considering the levels among opioid addicts, the likelihood of sleep pattern disruption and suicidal thoughts will be significant.

Table no 2 depicts that there is positive relation between Sleep patterns and Suicidal Ideation among opioid dependents and the sig value is 0.00, which is below 0.05. As a result, alternative hypothesis H2, which claims there is significant correlation between sleep patterns and suicidal ideation among opioid dependence is accepted

As shown in table 3 above the p value for effect of opioid drug on sleep patterns among opioid dependents is 0.00. As, P value being below 0.05, hence we will accept the alternate hypothesis, H3, which states that opioid dependence has a substantial impact on sleep patterns.

As shown in table 4 above the p value for effect of opioid drug on suicidal ideation among opioid dependents is 0.00. As, P value is below 0.05 and adopt an alternative hypothesis, H4, which asserts that there is an effect of opioid drug on suicidal ideation among opioid dependents.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study discussed the connection between sleep disorders and opioid addicts' suicide thinking, preparation, and attempts. Some noteworthy findings show that sleep difficulties and suicidal thoughts, intentions, or attempts may be more common among opioid users. To be able to generalise, we might propose a stronger correlation between sleep disorders and suicidal thoughts among opioid addicts. The conclusions in this article are still based on data with high rates of opiate usage, sleep issues, and suicide thoughts. The results of this study may be useful in teaching and public health preventative initiatives to promote greater awareness of sleep patterns, suicidal thoughts and attempts to suicide among opiate users.

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